

ASCORBIC ACID PROPERTIES, CHARACTERISTICS, DETERMINATION OF SUBSTANCE AUTHENTICITY

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Annotation. This scientific thesis contains information about the properties and characteristics of ascorbic acid.

Keywords: Ascorbic acid, Metabolism

Introductory part. Vitamin C (ascorbic acid (AA)) is well known for its antioxidant properties. Consequently, many other important aspects of this versatile molecule are often underestimated or even ignored. In this thesis, we have tried to highlight some of these aspects, such as the peculiarities of the AA biosynthetic pathway in different organisms, the remarkable function of AA as a co-substrate of many important dioxygenases, the role of AA . regeneration enzymes and certain pathways of AA catabolism, as well as the interesting function of AA in gene expression. Ascorbic acid plays an important role in various biosyntheses, for example, by activating the hydroxylation reactions of tropocollagen, bile acids and carnitine. It is also significantly involved in the poisoning of compounds by hydroxylation and maintaining the content of cytochrome P 450 in the liver.

The main part. Biochemistry of ascorbic acid synthesis, mechanism of antioxidant action and participation in anabolism, pharmacokinetics and excretion, immunomodulatory effect of exogenous ascorbic acid and participation in infectious diseases, influence on the pathogenesis of radiation and intoxication, and additional requirements are divided into. Adequate supply is important for the functioning of the immune system. The largest content of ascorbic acid is found in the pituitary gland, adrenal glands, and the lens of the eye, and varies depending on the load from 30 to 60 mg. After administration of ¹⁴C-labeled ascorbic acid, the compound is mainly stored in the brain, salivary glands, adrenal glands, testicles, and eye lens. For smokers, after surgery and injuries, as well as when there are infections, it is recommended to take 100 to 200 mg per day. A dose of more than 2 days leads to the inhibition of the phagocytosis activity of leukocytes. scorbic acid is a low molecular weight antioxidant, well known as vitamin C with anti-scurvy effects in humans, primates, and guinea pigs. Therefore, the synthesized natural compound presented a high potential for use in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

Summary section. In conclusion, it is worth saying that today ascorbic acid has a lot of useful properties. But the properties and aspects of its versatile molecule are often underestimated. Ascorbic acid is valued not only as an antioxidant, but also as a chemical compound that affects many pathways that have a beneficial effect on many diseases and processes in the human body.

References:

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